

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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MUNDARIJA

“Yashil universitet” tamoyillari: mazmun-mohiyati va ahamiyati	20
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
“Yashil universitet” tamoyili asosida barqaror rivojlanish rejasi va institutsional chora-tadbirlar amaliyoti	26
Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich	
O‘zbekistonda davlat mulkini xususiylashtirishning yangi bosqichiga o‘tmoqda	31
Shadmanov Erkin Sherkulovich	
The Impact of Technological Advancements on SME Growth: Trends and Case Studies in Uzbekistan	35
Tojiyev Abror, Raxmonaliyev Abbas	
Оценки эффективности деятельности малого бизнеса	45
Ортиков Улугбек Акробек угли	
Yashil iqtisodiyotda cheklangan resurslarning cheksiz imkoniyatlari	51
Saidov Muhammadali Hakimovich, Esanbekov Diyorbek Mirzabek o‘g‘li	
O‘zbekiston iqtisodiyotining barqaror rivojlanishida tijroat banklarining o‘rni	57
Xakimova Feruza Nazarovna	
Biznesning ijtimoiy ma‘suliyati konsepsiyasining rivojlanish bosqichlari	62
M.O. Kasimova	
Korporativ boshqaruvda risklarni boshqarish va risk darajasini pasaytirish yo‘llari	68
Mallayev Salohiddin Saidkamolovich	
Взаимосвязь стратегии управления персоналом и бизнес стратегии организации	74
Давлетов Ислom Халикович, Бикмаев Тимур Рафаелевич	
Iqtisodiyotning barqaror va izchil rivojlanishida ishlab chiqarishni mahalliyashtirishning o‘rni	78
Sobitova Ra‘no Solidjonovna	
Statistik kuzatuvlarni samarali tashkil qilishda raqamli texnologiyalardan keng foydalanishdagi mavjud muammolar	82
Istoraxon Abdusalomova Ilhom qizi	
Xizmat ko‘rsatish korxonalarida risklarni diversifikatsiya tahlili	87
Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o‘g‘li	
Korxonalarda raqamli marketing: nazariy asoslar va amaliy imkoniyatlar	94
Amonov Mirzohid Tuymuratovich	
Enhancing post-quantum security through hybrid cryptographic systems integrating quantum key distribution	98
Shuxrat Toirov Abduganiyevich, Saidakhmedov Eldor Islomovich, Akbarov X.U	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda elektron tijorat bozorining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati bo‘yicha adabiyotlar tahlili	110
Sodiqov Abdulhafiz	
Mulkiy soliqlar ma‘muriyatchiligi va ulardan soliq xavfsizligini ta‘minlashda foydalanish	118
Aliyarov Olim Abdug‘aparovich	
Mahalliy budjetlar daromadlarini shakllantirishda mahalliy soliqlar va yig‘imlarning o‘rni va ahamiyati	125
Bauyetdinov M.J., Eshbanbetov E.M.	
Yuk avtomobillari transport xizmatlarining samaradorligini aniqlash ko‘rsatkichlari	130
Mirzayev Qulmamat Jonuzoqovich, Ishonkulova Feruza Asatovna	
Arima modellari yordamida jismoniy shaxslarning xorijiy pul o‘tkazmalari ko‘satkichini prognozlashtirish (surxondaryo viloyatida)	135
Davranov Odil Jumanazarovich	
Kambag‘allikni baholash: AQSH misolida FPL	146
Durdona Davletova	
Ta‘lim xizmatlari sifatini oshirishning nazariy-ilmiy asoslari	151
Axmedova Barno Abdiyevna	

Tijorat banklarining depozit jalb qilishdagi o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	155
Farhod Rustamovich Bobobekov	
Трансформация потребительской этики и поведения в условиях перехода узбекистана к зеленой экономике.....	161
Хусайнов Равшан Рахимович, Кариева Латофат Саидакромовна	
Qurilish materiallari sanoati korxonalarining samarali innovatsion rivojlanishini ta'minlash yo'nalishlari	168
Fayzullayev Jonibek Mambetsaliy o'g'li	
Comparative analysis between the fundamental and technical analysis of stocks	175
To'qmirzayev Kamol Mo'min ugli	
Тенденции устойчивого развития автотранспортных предприятий в формировании цифровой экономики.....	182
Юсупходжаева Г.Б	
Влияние маркетинга на качество продукции – стратегии успешных брендов и использование отзывов клиентов	187
Маматкулова Шоира Джалоловна	
Ma'suliyati cheklangan jamiyatlarning fond bozoriga kirish imkoniyatlari: statistika, tahlil va prognozlar	192
Butayev Javlonbek Inatillo o'g'li	
O'zbekistoning eksport salohiyatini mustahkamlash zamonaviy tendensiyalari	197
Bozorov Akmal Amonovich	
Mintaqa salohiyatini oshirishda innovatsiyalar va investitsiyalarni rag'batlantirishda klaster yondashuvining o'rni.....	203
Muxammadiyeva Yulduz Yusupovna	
Инновационная деятельность металлургических предприятий в изменяющейся среде	207
Каримов Маъруф Ихтиёрович	
Значение лизинговых услуг в финансировании основного капитала предприятий	212
Латипова Шахноза Махмудовна	
Iqtisodiyotning jadal rivojlanishini innovatsion faoliyat asosida shakllantirish yo'llari	217
Nosir Maxmudov	
Davlat xaridlarida moliyaviy nazoratni amalga oshirish muammolari	224
Abdug'aniyev Bekjon Habibulla o'g'li	
Qishloq xo'jaligi korxonalarida kapital qo'yilmalar hisobini takomillashtirish	229
Baxriyev Muxiddin Sheraliyevich	
Main directions of increasing the investment attractiveness of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan	240
Kengesov Diyorbek Umidovich, Nurniyazova Dilnoza Arzubay qizi, Xalmuratova Dilnaz Suleyman qizi, Bekjanova Gozzal Janabaevna	
Исследование оказания торгового обслуживания сельского населения.....	245
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна, Усманова Дильфуза Ильхомовна	
Развитие логистики спортивных мероприятий на основе международной практики	252
Исмагулова Гульмира Нуралиевна	
Tijorat banklari depozit xizmatlari amaliyotini takomillashtirish	257
Melikov Otabek Maxmadaminovich	
Tijorat ko'chmas mulki qiymatini baholash xususiyatlari va unga ta'sir etuvchi omillar	263
Xomitov K.Z.	
Improvement of accounting of authorized capital at joint-stock companies	269
Ortikov Ergashjon Yakubboevich, Xusinov Ibragim Ismailovich	
Raqamli valyutaning xalqaro savdodagi roli: imkoniyatlar va muammolar.....	274
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, To'qmirzayev Kamol Mo'min o'g'li	
Yashil iqtisodiyot: nazariy jihatlar va ahamiyati	279
Maksumova Dildora Alisherovna	
O'zbekistonda raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlanish asoslari.....	283
Maxmudova Feruzabonu Odiljon qizi, Lutfiy Farangiz Sharidin qizi	
Oziq-ovqat sanoatini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari	288
Tursunova Dilnavoz davron qizi	

Национальная оценка рисков отмывание преступных доходов	294
Хомидов Шухрат Гафуржонович	
Inflyatsion targetlash rejimiga asoslangan monetar siyosatning makroiqtisodiy ahamiyati	301
Duskobilov Umidjon Sharofiddinovich	
Tijorat banklarining kredit mablag'laridan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	308
Ulugbek Nizamov	
Soliq bazasini aniqlash metodologiyasining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va tamoyillari.....	312
Xalikchayeva Sadokat Ilxomjonovna	
"Qishloq xo'jaligida innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish va ularning iqtisodiy samaradorligi"	316
Shamshetova Gulraushan Sarsenovna	
Повышение популярности банковских услуг посредством цифровых инноваций: стратегии интеграции технологий с ориентацией на клиента	318
Рузиева Олима Шухратовна, Рузиев Шухрат Нармурадович	
Tovar-moddiy resurslar harakatini samarali ta'minlashda xorijiy tajribalar	322
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev	
Pul-kredit siyosatida "big data" texnologiyalari: o'zbekistonda to'lov ma'lumotlari, qidiruv so'rovlari va matn tahlilidan foydalanish istiqbollari	327
Mamatxo'jayev Otabek Farxodjon o'g'li	
O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida tijorat banklarining moliyaviy barqarorligini mustahkamlash	332
Abdusamatov Mamaysup Qulmonovich, Jovliyev Ramazon Fazriddin o'g'li	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarini soliqqa tortishda chet el tajribasi.....	343
A.I. Akbarov	
Mamlakatda kichik biznes subyektlari va eksport sohasida samarali rivojlanish yo'nalishlari	347
M.A.Ibrohimov	
Neighborhood system of activity economic the basics improvement	351
Alikulov Ravshan Shodiyor o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari evolyutsiyasi va kapitallashuv darajasini oshirishning iqtisodiy asoslari.....	356
Mamadjonov Shukurillo Ibrohimjon o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda tijorat banklarning anderryayting jarayonlarini takomillashtirishni innovatsion usullari	360
Bobojonov Xursand Qadamovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasida pensiya jamg'armasi faoliyatini takomillashtirish	374
Inoyatova Maqsuda Palvonnazirovna	
"Yashil iqtisodiyot" iqtisodiyotning barqaror rivojlanish asosi sifatida.....	379
Jiemuratov Temirbay Polatbaevich, Muratbaev Bayram Bazarbay uli	
Aholining daromadlarini soliqqa tortish asosida tengsizlikni kamaytirish yo'llari.....	384
Vosiqov Ulug'bek Alisherovich	
Soliq to'lovchilarga ko'rsatiladigan raqamli xizmatlarni ko'paytirish orqali soliq bazasini kengaytirish.....	389
Usmonov Ulug'bek Jaxongir o'g'li	
Совершенствование механизмов стимулирования инновационного развития промышленности: международный опыт и перспективы для узбекистана.....	394
Ўролова Севара Бехзод кизи	
Стратегия перехода к зеленой экономике Республики Узбекистан.....	399
Маматова Фатима Абдусаломовна	
Ensuring financial stability of companies international practice experience	405
Abdullayeva Madinabonu Khasanboyevna	

LITERATURE REVIEW OF THE TOPIC

The indicators of financial stability of Joint-Stock Companies and their methods of identification are varied by foreign and economic scientists of our country the approach and tariffs were cited. Ch.Fridman and K.Gudlet believed that determining the financial stability indicators of companies is inherently complex being a process, it does not make it possible to form a complete picture of the state of financial stability of specific indicators itself. Especially since the World Economic and financial crises in recent years have been observed, these indicators are observed in every a comprehensive study assumes reaching [2]. J.G.Shirazi believed that the financial system is stable if an effective distribution of economic resources, financial risks, their assessment and management is carried out. Through this definition, the author is considered an important aspect of achieving financial stability, that is, focusing precisely on assessing risks and managing them [3].

S.V.Kulikov considers the financial stability of the company on the basis of two different approaches. In particular, according to the first approach, this (financial stability) is understood as "The presence of a fixed share of equity in the total amount of financial instruments, and in accordance with the second approach, the efficiency of distribution and use for the growth of capital and profit in maintaining the state of financial resources, solvency and creditworthiness of the enterprise"[4]. A.P.Arkipov believes that the concept of financial stability can be defined as the ability of a company to fulfill its obligations to other participants in the market today and in the future [5].

According to Professor T.S. Malikov, the financial stability of business entities is expressed through general (autonomy coefficient, debt capital concentration coefficient, debt-to-equity ratio) and relative indicators (reserve and expense coverage by equity coefficient, financial independence coefficient, equity turnover coefficient) [6]. According to Professor A.U. Burkhanov, financial stability is a complex indicator of a company's operations based on the ability to generate profit, repay debts, finance its activities, and the steady development of resource turnover rates [7]. Professor O.N. Khambdamov emphasizes that financial stability monitoring of companies refers to the regular observation, analysis, and forecasting of the indicators that ensure financial stability, as well as the decision-making of tactical and strategic choices, and evaluating the effectiveness of the decisions made [8].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the research process, the scientific and theoretical aspects of developing a financial stability strategy in joint-stock companies were studied. A comparative analysis was conducted on the organization of financial stability monitoring and the current state of financial strategies in the practices of foreign companies. The study relied on numerous theoretical literature sources and empirical research, making extensive use of logical thinking, scientific reflection, and systematic approach methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As the economy develops, the cooperation between countries continues to grow. Based on the opportunities for socio-economic development and trends in trade relations between countries, similarities in the types and standards of financial reporting are shaped. While analyzing international best practices aimed at enhancing the financial stability of companies, we observe that among the G7 countries, the United States stands out due to its high level of economic development, strong macroeconomic trends, and widespread corporate business models. Many multinational companies have their headquarters located in the U.S. For instance, major multinational companies such as Wal-Mart, Amazon Inc., Apple Inc., Berkshire Hathaway, and JP Morgan Chase & Co. can be cited as examples. In this scientific article, we will analyze the main financial activities of JP Morgan Chase & Co., one of the world's largest multinational corporations. The corporation's headquarters is located in New York City, and it is a U.S.-based multinational investment bank and financial services holding company registered in the state of Delaware.

As of the end of 2022, JP Morgan Chase & Co. is one of the largest banks in the world by market capitalization in the U.S. and ranks as the fifth-largest bank globally in terms of total assets, amounting to 3.95 trillion USD [9]. Additionally, JP Morgan Chase & Co. ranks 24th on the Fortune 500 list of the largest U.S. corporations by total revenue (Global 500 - The largest companies in the world by revenue). It is worth noting that the key financial indicators of JP Morgan Chase & Co. have shown a growth trend in the post-Covid-19 pandemic period (Figure 1). Specifically, total net income in 2022 increased by 18.4% compared to 2021, while non-interest expenses and provisions for credit losses decreased relative to revenue. The main reason for this is that the corporation made large payments on its corporate bonds during this period (pic.1).

Picture 1. Analysis of financial indicators of JP Morgan Chase & Co. Corporation (billion US dollars) [10].

JP Morgan Chase & Co. is considered a “Bulge Bracket” bank and is a leading provider of various investment banking and financial services. Along with Bank of America, Citigroup, and Wells Fargo, it is one of the “Big Four” banks in the United States. The corporation’s total assets increased by 2% compared to 2021, reaching 3,743.56 million USD (Table 1). According to the table, provisions for credit losses amounted to 6.4 billion USD, which includes a net addition of 3.5 billion USD and a net reduction of 2.9 billion USD. Market data shows that the company’s stock value reached 158.35 million USD, representing a 24% increase compared to 2020. By the end of 2021, the value of common stock was 2,944.1 million USD, which directly contributed to an average 8.9% growth in capitalization. The company’s net income grew by 6.3% compared to the previous year, reaching 13.4 billion USD, or 4.44 USD per share, which was significantly higher than the consensus estimate of 4.17 USD per share. At the same time, the return on equity (ROE) increased significantly to 17%, with income rising by 8.2% to 42.5 billion USD, surpassing Wall Street analysts’ average estimate of 41.7 billion USD. In 2023, an increase in loan volume and an 8-fold increase in the net interest margin resulted in a 11.4% rise in net profit, reaching 23.2 billion USD (table 1).

Table 1. JP Morgan Chase&Co Corporation consolidated balance sheet analysis (mln. US Dollar) [11].

	Specification	2021	2022	Changes
1.	Money resources and funds in banks	26,438	27,697	5%
2.	Deposits in banks	714,39	539,53	(24)
3.	Government securities	261,69	315,59	21
4.	Debt visibility securities	206,07	185,36	(10)
5.	Commercial assets	433,57	453,79	5
6.	Securities available for sale	308,52	205,85	(33)
7.	Securities held before expiration	363,7	425,3	17
8.	Investment securities	672,23	631,16	(6)
9.	Credits	1077,71	1135,64	5
10.	Reserve to cover losses on credit	(16,386)	(19,726)	20
11.	Loans, taking into account reserves for losses on loans	1061,32	1115,92	5
12.	Accrued interest and receivables	102,57	125,18	22
13.	Basic tools and equipment	27,07	27,73	2
14.	Goodwill, MSR and other intangible assets	56,69	60,85	7
15.	Other assets	181,49	182,88	1
16.	Total assets	3743,56	3665,74	(2)%

According to data from Trading Economics, corporate profits in the United States increased by 9.1% in the second quarter of 2022, reaching a new record of 2.62 trillion USD, following a decline of 4.9% in the previous period. The internal funds available for investment by corporations, along with inventory valuation, increased by 5.8%, totaling 3.34 trillion USD, while net dividends decreased by 0.2%, amounting to 1.47 trillion USD. At the same time, retained earnings rose by 23.8%, reaching 1.15 trillion USD [12].

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

For 2024, JPMorgan's management continues to forecast a net income of approximately 90 billion USD and operating expenses of around 91 billion USD (a 4.4% increase). Furthermore, it is planned to enhance opportunities for diversifying prospective investment projects by maintaining the positive indicators of most financial stability metrics. According to the company's management forecasts, ongoing geopolitical tensions and persistent inflationary pressures may negatively impact trade relations.

Currently, even in developed countries, there are no unified legal standards or specific restrictions regarding the digitization of corporate valuations, the use of artificial intelligence, or working with large data repositories. In Uzbekistan, however, recent years have seen the publication of legal documents aimed at digitization and sector development. Additionally, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed a decree approving the "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" strategy and measures for its effective implementation. This has created a legal and fundamental foundation for the development of this sector, with a roadmap and strategy being established, which will guide large-scale projects, digital technologies, and similar digital products in the coming years.

Financial stability is a complex, multi-element system that manifests across all areas of a company's financial activities. Analyzing financial stability should address not only issues of asset composition and financing sources optimization but also technical-economic, financial security, and profitability matters, which fundamentally represent the long-term stability of economic activity. In foreign practice, the issue of optimizing capital structure within a systematic analysis framework is typically addressed using the method of calculating the financial leverage ratio. The impact of financial leverage is reflected in the positive deviation between economic profitability and the average interest rate on credit, which is often referred to as the financial leverage differential in foreign practice. If the difference is positive, any increase in the financial leverage ratio leads to a further increase in equity profitability.

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